

Turning Ammonia Emissions Into Sustainable Fertiliser

Ammonia, produced by pig slurry, pollutes the air in barns and the environment. It damages the respiratory health of animals and farm workers.

Conventional ventilation systems try to improve the air quality in pig houses by exchanging the air.

An advanced ammonia air washing unit captures ammonia directly from the air and prevents it from escaping, as the ammonia is absorbed by a sulfuric acid solution. This produces **ammonia sulfate**, a liquid fertiliser for crop production.

Benefits:

- Ammonia reduction up to 62%
- Saves money and emissions